

Concepts around real-time trading for physical and / or virtual stocks with software system:

Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime.

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Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime implements a trading platform based on Enterprise Resource Planning Software [Yerith-Erp-9.0-PLATINUM](#);

VERSION: December 1, 2024

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

THIS chapter motivates the need for creating Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime here in Africa.

1.1 Goods Exchanges as part of QUALITY life

Figure 1.1: Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime check-in stocks; a window; for all services.

TODAY, for instance, Cameroon republic doesn't possess its own money currency; BUT uses a sub-money derived and backed by the EUROPEAN-UNION currency Euros (€).

THIS situation creates following in order of importance problems and facts :

- **THE fluctuation and the volume (quantities) of stocks-goods exchanges has a limitation and its not infinitely limited as it shall be naturally;**

When an african country possesses its own currency-money, it could create as many coins and bills as it needs to practice commerce as exchanges of goods,;

Because I am not a specialist and / or practitioner in economy; and / or in finance or financial market; I AM INCOMPETENT in giving any scientific and / or engineering literature book-citation that amplifies and / or corroborates my previous statement.

Chapter 2

ALGORITHM DESIGN SCHEME

THIS chapter says what must be achieved by our program **Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime** as requirements so to alleviate mistakes and unfair inventory stock exchanges.

2.1 Requirements for Equitable and Fair Inventory Stock Exchanges

Table 2.1: Client / CUSTOMERS selling and buying order keywords and their Meaning.

Client ORDER / OTHER orders	REVERSED order	MEANINGS
1. <i>start-exchange-only-order</i>	<i>stop-exchange-only-order</i>	ORDER an exchange-only process.
2. <i>stop-exchange-only-order</i>	<i>start-exchange-only-order</i>	Stops an exchange-only process.
3. <i>start-buying-order</i>	<i>stop-buying-order</i>	Starts a buying-order process.
4. <i>stop-buying-order</i>	<i>start-buying-order</i>	Stops a buying-order process.
5. <i>start-selling-order</i>	<i>stop-selling-order</i>	ORDER a selling-only process.
6. <i>stop-selling-order</i>	<i>start-selling-order</i>	STOPS a selling process.
7. <i>start-selling-MARKET (X)</i>	<i>stop-selling-MARKET (X)</i>	Starts a market sales now.
8. <i>stop-selling-MARKET (X)</i>	<i>start-selling-MARKET (X)</i>	Stops a market sales now.

- o EACH customer / client of **Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime** has certain time-frame where HE puts his order request; ALL type of order request are illustrated and briefly explained in TABLE 2.1;
- o EACH market that is handled by **Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime** has opening and closing hours that have to be respected by clients-customers.

2.1.1 Client / CUSTOMER ORDERS REQUESTS

1. **A client / customer ORDER contains following elements that are defined by both client / customer and market managers:**
 - a. START time of order;
 - b. CLOSING time of order, IF ORDER not already executed by **Yerith-Erp-9.0-Trading-realtime**;
 - c. TYPE of order : sell, buy, exchange-only;
 - d. VOID if no issue satisfied; OR send to next open market time-frame to retry to accomplish successfully order.
2. **ALL orders that could not be executed during a market order opening hours are voided; There is reimbursement option for a client / customer;**

There is an automatic selectable option to resend the client / customer order onto the next opening market hours For an additional non-imposing fee.

2.1.2 Pre-CONDITIONS for a fair TRADING Exchange realtime Algorithm

1. THE trading exchange algorithm "A" has a start time and an end time;
2. Each algorithm that shall run concurrently to another algorithm shall be run within a database transaction on a specified table column value.
3. An internal and an external algorithm condition shall be enabled so to allow interruption of a running algorithm whenever it doesn't terminate after an user defined unacceptable running time "algorithm_running_time(A)" :
 - Concretely, implementation-wise, THERE will be a database table named "DB_TABLE_algorithm_RUNNING_TIME" where a timeout time-frame interval shall be specified for each algorithm-thread so that : WHENEVER an algorithm is still running after a certain pre-defined time-interval, ITS thread of execution shall be interrupted : This for instance could be achieved using the "kill -9" command.

Chapter 3

Algorithmic TRADING with YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF

THIS chapter motivates the need for trading on conditions with trade-time; AND how to perform this using YERITH_QVGE.

3.1 TRADING with conditions on Trade-time.

Figure 3.1: YRI_QVGE for trading stock exchanges using programmatic conditions on trading-timing.

The screenshot shows the YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF console interface. At the top, there is a menu bar with 'Actions', 'Tools', and 'HELP'. Below the menu bar is a toolbar with various icons. A search bar is present with the placeholder text 'Enter "source" or "SQL event" for filtering', along with 'Reset' and 'Filter' buttons. Below the search bar are four tabs: 'SQL Error Event Reporting Logging', 'SQL Event Logging', 'Console logging raw', and 'Runtime Verification Monitors'. The main area displays a table with the following data:

time stamp	sql error event log	source	target	changed qty	runtime monitor ID
1 21:58:55:419	'SELECT.departements_produits'	yerith-erp-pgi-9.0	YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF	1	0

Below the table, the 'runtime monitor name' is set to 'YERITH_QVGE_sample_PAPER_extended_version_PROPERTY'. The console shows the following details for the selected event:

TIME STAMP	SQL recovered executed query
1 21:58:55:419	Insert into departements_produits (id, nom_departement_produit) values ((SELECT id FROM departements_produits ORDER BY id DESC LIMIT 0, 1), 'YRI_ASSET');

Source file and line number:

1) source file	2) line number
1 src/yerith-erp-windows.cpp	992

Pre-condition and post-condition details:

3) (before) pre-condition on source state		4) (after) post-condition on target state	
1	not_in_before(YRI_ASSET, departements_produits.nom_departement_produit)	1	in_after(YRI_ASSET, stocks.nom_departement_produit)

Guarded condition expression and state details:

6) evaluated guarded condition expression	value	7) previous state		
1 in_sql_event_log ('DELETE.departements_produits.YRI_ASSET', STATE(YRI))	True	1	YRI	E
			accepting state	is error state
				True

At the bottom of the console, a message states: 'YRI-DB-RUNTIME-VERIF: this console is registered to the system d-bus as service: 'yri.db-runtime.verif'.'

Figure 3.2: A SCREENSHOT OF YRI_QVGE: HOW to design state conditions on trade-time.

Chapter 4

Conclusion
